

**INFLUENCE OF NORMAL LOAD FREQUENCY
ON FRETTING FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR BY
A CRITICAL PLANE-BASED APPROACH**

Sabrina Vantadori¹, Farshad Abbasi², Andrea Zanichelli¹,
Davide Leonetti³, Giovanni Pio Pucillo⁴,
Gholam Hossein Majzooobi⁵

¹Department of Engineering and Architecture,
University of Parma
Parco Area delle Scienze 181/a, 43124 Parma, Italy

²Department of Mechanical and Industrial Production,
Mondragon Unibertsitatea
Loramendi 4, 20500 Arrasate, Mondragon, Spain

³Department of the Built Environment,
Eindhoven University of Technology
De Zaale 5612 AZ, Eindhoven, The Netherlands

⁴Department of Industrial Engineering
University of Naples Federico II
P.le V. Tecchio 80, 80125 Naples, Italy

⁵Mechanical Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering, Bu-
Ali Sina University, Hamadan, Iran

ABSTRACT

In the last decades, many catastrophic events due to the rupture of metallic components have been traced back to fretting fatigue. In order to avoid failures due to such a contact phenomenon, many

researchers have focused on fretting fatigue behaviour of different materials. In the present work, an experimental campaign carried out on an Al7075-T6 aluminium alloy is simulated by employing a multi-axial fatigue criterion proposed for fretting fatigue. The configuration simulated is a flat-to-flat bridge-shaped contact, characterised by cyclic normal load, with different frequencies, as well as different level of fatigue loading applied to the specimen.

KEYWORDS

Bridge testing, cyclic normal load, fretting fatigue, multi-axial criterion

1. INTRODUCTION

Many in-service engineering components are affected by fatigue damage. In fact, a fatigue loading acting on a structural component is able to promote the evolution of cracks, potentially leading to the failure of the fatigued component itself. Such cracks may originate in regions characterised by high stress levels, in correspondence of stress raisers, that is either defects, inclusions, voids, or notches [1-4].

Surface cracks may also nucleate due to the relative motion along the interface of two bodies in contact [5]. By considering at least one of the bodies under contact experiencing a fatigue loading, the above superficial cracks may evolve. Consequently, the failure of the fatigued component may occur. This situation is referred to as fretting fatigue [6].

When the amplitude of the relative motion between the bodies in contact is of the order of a few microns, a partial slip regime takes place between the contact surfaces. In particular, the contact zone consists of an inner stick region, with no relative displacements, and an outer micro-slip region, characterised by relative micro-displacements.

In such a condition, high stress gradients arise in the vicinity of the contact surface, which are responsible for the nucleation of superficial micro-cracks [7]. On the other hand, the amount of superficial wear is negligible in partial slip condition [8]. Consequently, it is widely accepted by the scientific community that the considerable reduction in lifetime caused by fretting fatigue,

with respect to plain fatigue [9], is related to the stress concentration and the stress gradient phenomena associated with the contact problem. More in detail, the fretting fatigue problem in partial slip regime has been compared to the problem of fatigued notched components, and a notch stress-based methodology has been successfully applied to fretting fatigue in the medium/high cycle fatigue regime [10].

However, fretting fatigue is a complex phenomenon, which is affected by more than fifty parameters [11]. During the last decades, a considerable amount of researches have been developed with the aim to increase knowledge about fretting fatigue. In particular, numerous experimental campaigns have been carried out, and different test apparatuses have been designed. Two categories of fretting fatigue test methods can be distinguished: structure-based methods [12-16] and material-based methods [17-34].

Structure-based fretting fatigue test methods are generally employed in order to reproduce in laboratory the fretting fatigue behaviour of a specific in-service structural component. In this case, the results obtained are directly correlated to the real engineering problem, thus avoiding any extrapolations or generalizations. Many examples of full-scale testing are available in the literature. The fretting fatigue behaviour of an aluminium alloy in contact with steel in an oil drill pipe connection was analysed by Santus [14]. In terms of fatigue life, a reduction by a factor of 2.7 was observed in comparison to the aluminium alloy plain fatigue life. Azevedo et al. [15] designed a fretting fatigue

test rig for overhead conductors, in order to obtain the S-N curve related to middle-high cycle fatigue regime of a steel reinforced aluminium conductor. An experimental campaign was carried out by O'Halloran et al. [16] with the aim to quantify both friction coefficient and wear coefficient of a dynamic flexible marine riser made of a 080M40 steel.

Nevertheless, experimental tests designed to investigate the fretting fatigue behaviour of a specific in-service structural component are generally expensive and time consuming. Moreover, the influence of the different sizes affecting the contact problem (that is, contact dimension, relative displacement amplitude, and surface roughness) should be taken into careful consideration. As a matter of fact, it is very difficult to exactly reproduce the real contact problem and, consequently, it may happen that the results related to a test specimen, nominally identical to the real component, turn out to be unreliable [5].

On the other hand, *material-based fretting fatigue test methods* are typically employed in order to investigate the influence of different contact parameters on the fretting fatigue behaviour relatively to a specific material. Such parameters include contact geometry [19], surface treatments [20,21], temperature [22], amount of relative displacement [23], and loading conditions [24,25]. In this case, the results obtained are intended to be extrapolated to a wide range of contact problems, even significantly different from those considered in the experimental testing.

According to this kind of test, simple and well-defined contact geometries are employed in test rigs. More precisely, either cylinder-to-flat, sphere-to-flat, or flat-to-flat contact configurations are employed, since analytical closed-form solutions for such contacts are available. The typical arrangement involves two fretting pads, clamped against a flat specimen by means of a constant normal load. Note that either stand-alone pads or bridge-shaped pads may be chosen, as shown schematically in **Figures 1(a)** and **(b)**, respectively. Simultaneously, the specimen is subjected to a fatigue loading, that can be cyclic either bending or tension.

Figure 1.

Nishioka and Hirakawa [26], Bramhall [27], and Nowell [28] carried out experimental tests with cylindrical stand-alone pads by employing testing apparatuses equipped with a single actuator devoted to the cyclic loading on the specimen, where the tangential load is in-phase with the cyclic loading. Even experimental campaigns on flat specimens in contact with spherical stand-alone pads are available in the literature [29,30]. Bridge-shaped pads have been employed to investigate the fretting behaviour under both flat-to-flat and cylinder-to-flat contact configurations [31,32].

In order to apply the tangential load independently of the fatigue load, a two-actuators fretting device should be employed [33]. More recently, a four actuators fretting device has been

developed at the University of Brasilia [34], with the aim to analyse the influence of each load involved in the fretting fatigue problem.

In the last decades, many researchers have focused on fretting fatigue behaviour of different materials, tested by considering both a constant normal load and in-phase fretting fatigue loading [35-45]. However, more complex loading conditions generally affect in-service engineering components. In such a context, some papers concerning complex loading configurations have been recently proposed. Iyer and Mall [46] observed a reduction in terms of fatigue life of a Ti-6Al-4V when the constant normal load is increased in presence of a low frequency fatigue loading (1Hz) acting on the specimen, whereas the opposite occurred in the case of a high frequency (200Hz). Lee and Mall [47] and Talemi et al. [48] have investigated the effect of a phase angle between axial fatigue load and cyclic tangential load on a Ti-6Al-4V and a Al2024-T3, respectively. It was observed that phase shift influenced surface slip, crack initiation location, and fatigue life. More precisely, a phase angle of 180° has been found to promote cracks to nucleate at the edge of the contact on the opposite side with respect to the in-phase condition [49], whereas when a phase angle of 90° was considered the fatigue life improved and cracks were able to initiate on both sides of the contact, that is either at the trailing edge or at the leading edge [50]. More recently, Abbasi and Majzoubi [25,51] published a comprehensive study regarding the effect of cyclic normal load and out-of-phase loading on fretting behaviour of an Al7075-T6. In such a work, different frequencies of the normal

load have been considered. The fatigue life was observed to increase when the normal load and the fatigue load were out-of-phase, whereas it was found to decrease for higher values of normal load, for each level of fatigue load considered.

In the present paper, the experimental tests carried out by Majzoubi and Abbasi [25] on an Al7075-T6 aluminium alloy are simulated by employing a critical plane-based multiaxial criterion formulated for fretting fatigue [52-54]. Such a criterion was previously applied to different fretting fatigue problems, on either cylindrical- or spherical-to-flat contact configurations, with a constant normal load applied to the pads. In this study, instead, the criterion is applied for the first time to a flat-to-flat bridge-shaped contact, with a cyclic normal load applied to the pads. Moreover, a cyclic axial load applied to the specimen is also considered. As a matter of fact, the novelty of the present paper is that to check if the criterion is able to simulate the influence of the normal load frequency, experimentally observed in the aforementioned campaign [25] on both crack initiation and lifetime.

The paper is structured as follows. The experimental campaign analysed is described in **Section 2**, in terms of fretting apparatus, specimen geometry, material properties, loading conditions, and experimental results. Then, **Section 3** is devoted to the description of both the finite element numerical model [51], employed for the determination of the stress state within the specimen, and the aforementioned multiaxial criterion [52-54] used to simulate the experimental tests. The theoretical results obtained are discussed

in **Section 4**, in terms of both crack initiation and fatigue life. Finally, conclusions are outlined in **Section 5**. Furthermore, **Appendix A** contains a detailed presentation of the multiaxial criterion for fretting fatigue.

2. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

The fretting fatigue tests, carried out by Majzoobi and Abbasi [25] on an Al7075-T6 aluminium alloy, are described in this Section. In more detail, such an experimental campaign is illustrated in terms of fretting apparatus, specimen geometry, material properties, loading conditions, and experimental results.

2.1 Fretting apparatus

A fretting apparatus, originally developed by Majzoobi et al. [31] for fretting tests under constant normal load, has been modified in order to perform fretting fatigue tests under cyclic normal load (see **Figure 2(a)**).

Figure 2.

In particular, such a cyclic normal load, P , was characterised by a loading ratio $R=0$ and could be applied with a maximum frequency equal to 200Hz , by means of two servomotors linked to the fretting pads. A closed-loop master-slave control method was employed for the synchronization of the normal load applied to each fretting pad.

In more detail, the master controller provided real-time information to the slave one, so that the two servomotors were started and stopped at the same time, and kept with both synchronous speed and position for the whole experiment.

Furthermore, the specimen was subjected to a cyclic axial load, B , applied independently of the normal load, P , by means of a variable crank system. More precisely, a stepped eccentric shaft was connected to an eccentric bush bearing, so that a transversal motion, equal to $2mm$, was obtained for a complete revolution of the shaft. This cyclic transversal displacement for the shaft-bush assembly was converted to a cyclic vertical displacement of two horizontal plates, which was responsible for the cyclic axial load experienced by the specimen.

The normal load applied to each fretting pad was monitored during the test in order to verify that each side of the specimen experienced the same normal pressure in correspondence with a generic time instant. To this aim, two piezoelectric load cells were fixed on the pads in order to measure the values of the applied normal load. Moreover, a DSCK load cell was dedicated to monitoring the applied axial load. The values of both the normal load and the axial load, measured from the load cells, were collected by means of a Kistler data acquisition system.

It is important to highlight that the pads were designed in order to be characterised by high rigidity. Moreover, rigid holder disks were installed on each side of the specimen, as shown in **Figure 2(b)**, in order to avoid the vertical displacement of the pads. In such a

way, the rotation of the entire contact system was negligible, and a precise alignment of the pads was assured.

2.2 Specimen geometry and material properties

Dog-bone test specimens, shown in **Figure 3(a)**, were used [25]. Two bridge-shaped pads, shown in **Figure 3(b)**, were clamped against the inner flat part of the specimen by means of the normal load, P . The contact surfaces of such pads were characterised by a flat profile and, consequently, the contact type was flat-to-flat.

Figure 3.

The specimens were made of Al 7075-T6 aluminium alloy, whose chemical composition was Al 90%, Zn 5.48%, Mg 2.33%, Cu 1.52%, Fe 0.47%, Cr 0.2%, Si 0.2%, Mn 0.08%, Ti 0.015% (percentages by weight). The mechanical properties were determined by Majzooobi et al. [25] by testing specimens extracted from the same Al 7075-T6 sheet used for fretting fatigue test specimens. Both material fatigue properties and grain size were not investigated in the above experimental campaign. They have been found in the literature for a similar Al 7075-T6 [55-57]: more precisely, the microstructure consists of long strip grain, with average dimensions equal to about $100\mu\text{m}$ and $30\mu\text{m}$ in the longitudinal and transversal directions, respectively. Therefore, an average grain size equal to $55\mu\text{m}$ has been computed as the radius of the circle equivalent to the ellipse having axes equal to the material grain dimensions along the two

orthogonal directions [58]. Both mechanical and fatigue properties of Al 7075-T6 are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1.

The fretting pads were made of SS 410 stainless steel. Such a material was selected due to its high resistance against oxidation and abrasion, with the aim to avoid that superficial debris, due to the wear of the pads, may affect the contact problem. The mechanical properties of SS 410 are summarised in **Table 1** [25].

Note that typical values of friction coefficient between Al 7075-T6 aluminium alloy and SS 410 stainless steel range from 0.38 to 0.44 [59].

2.3 Loading conditions and results

Four groups of tests were performed in order to experimentally investigate the effect of the normal load frequency [25]:

- a reference group (specimens from No. R1 to No. R5 in **Table 2**) characterised by a constant normal load equal to $1200N$;
- and three groups (specimens from No. T1 to No. T15 in **Table 3**) characterised by a cyclic normal load (with a loading ratio $R=0$ and maximum value equal to $P_{\max}=1200N$), and with a frequency f_p alternatively equal to $1Hz$ (specimens from No. T1 to No. T5 in **Table 3**), $5Hz$ (specimens from No. T6 to No. T10 in **Table 3**) and $10Hz$ (specimens from No. T10 to No. T15 in **Table 3**).

For each of the above groups, five different levels of the maximum value of the cyclic axial bulk load, B_{\max} , were considered (with loading ratio $R=0$ and frequency equal to 10Hz), so that the specimen experienced a maximum value of the cyclic axial bulk stress, $\sigma_{B,\max}$, equal to 130, 150, 180, 200 and 260MPa .

For the specimens from No. T1 to No. T15, **Figure 4** shows the time history of both the cyclic normal load and the cyclic bulk axial load, normalised with respect to P_{\max} and B_{\max} , respectively.

Table 2.

Table 3.

Figure 4.

It is worth noticing that, due to the above loading condition the nucleation of cracks is promoted in correspondence to the two trailing edges closest to the applied cyclic bulk axial load (see **Figure 1(b)**) that is, the crack nucleation sites are potentially two.

In the examined experimental campaign, cracks always initiated in correspondence of the upper trailing edge [25], as it is shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5.

The experimental crack initiation direction was detected for some specimens by employing a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The experimental cracks for test specimens No. R3, T3, T8, and T13 are shown in **Figures 6(a)-(d)**, respectively.

Figure 6.

The crack initiation direction, θ_{exp} , ranging from 27° to 41° inward the contact region, was measured with respect to a line perpendicular to the contact surface (a positive value is assumed within the contact zone).

No significant correlation between the experimental crack initiation direction and the normal load frequency was observed.

It is important to highlight that all the tests were characterised by a partial slip condition. In fact, optical microscopy images of the wear scars on the contact surface have proved the presence of both an inner smooth region, corresponding to the stick region, and an outer rough region, corresponding to the slip region [25]. The slip region was wider in the case of cyclic normal load with respect to constant normal load and, consequently, larger relative displacements arose in tests No. T1-T15 with respect to tests No. R1-R5, particularly in case of a low normal load frequency, f_p . Accordingly, for a given value of $\sigma_{B,max}$, it was observed that the specimens subjected to cyclic normal loading (see **Table 3**) were characterised by lower values of fatigue lifetime (that

is N_{exp}) with respect to those related to the reference group (see **Table 2**), and N_{exp} generally increased by increasing f_P .

Moreover, by taking as the reference lifetime that related to a constant normal load, the absolute value of the relative difference in terms of N_{exp} , computed with respect to the above reference value, was more severe by decreasing the value of $\sigma_{B,max}$, as shown in **Figure 7**, and such a difference generally decreased by increasing f_P .

Figure 7.

3. FRETTING FATIGUE ASSESSMENT

3.1 The finite element numerical model

A finite element numerical model [51] was used in order to compute the stress field produced within the specimen in the above fretting fatigue tests. Note that, such a stress field, in addition to the data listed in **Table 1**, are the input data required by the criterion employed for the fretting fatigue assessment (see Appendix A).

A bi-dimensional finite element numerical model was developed by employing the commercial software ABAQUS. The model discretisation is shown in **Figure 8**. Note that, only one quarter of the contact test configuration was considered in the simulation, due to the fact that the problem was assumed to be symmetric, as previously presented in Section 2.1. Moreover, a plane strain condition was assumed. Four-node quadrilateral elements (CPE4R type elements) were used in

the simulations. A total number of finite elements equal to 48264 were employed.

Figure 8.

The numerical model was characterised by a very refined mesh close to the contact surface for the first microns in depth, with elements having a maximum edge size of about $10\mu m$. Such a fine mesh was defined after a convergence procedure carried out by considering the maximum principal stress within the specimen along the contact surface (that is, $-1 \leq x \leq 1mm$). In particular, according to the convergence procedure detailed in Ref. [51], the convergence of the FE solution was assumed to be achieved when the results difference between two successive steps was less than 2%. Therefore, a high level of accuracy was assured, and the high stress gradients in the vicinity of the contact surface were properly captured.

Regarding the modelling of the contact interface, a master-slave interaction algorithm was used to describe the interaction between the specimen and the pad. More in detail, the contact surface of the fretting pad was defined as the master surface, whereas the contact surface of the specimen was defined as the slave one. Additionally, the Lagrange multiplier approach was included for the evaluation of friction in the contact region. The friction coefficient was taken equal to 0.4, in accordance with experimental observations [59].

A bilinear elastoplastic behaviour with kinematic hardening was assumed for the specimen, whereas an elastic model was considered for the pad.

Furthermore, both normal and axial loads were applied incrementally at different loading steps, according to the test procedure, in order to take into account possible kinematic effects at the contact interface.

The stress field in close proximity of the contact surface, that is $-1.5 \leq x \leq 1.5 \text{ mm}$ and $z=0$, is plotted for the specimen No. R1 (**Figure 9**) and No. T1 (**Figure 10**) at different time instants during the fretting cycle which period is equal to 0.1sec and 1 sec, respectively.

Figure 9.

Figure 10.

3.3 The multiaxial criterion for fretting fatigue

The multiaxial criterion for fretting fatigue proposed by Carpinteri et al. [52-54] is here employed in order to simulate the experimental campaign described in Section 2. In Appendix A, a detailed description of the multiaxial criterion for fretting fatigue is reported.

Once the stress field is computed along the longitudinal middle-cross section of the specimen, by means of the FE numerical model described in Section 3.1, the material point S (verification point),

where to perform the fatigue life evaluation, needs to be located within the specimen.

Firstly, the point on the contact surface, named hot-spot, H , is looked for. Then, the critical plane orientation is determined according to the Critical Direction Method proposed by Araújo et al. [60], and both the amplitude, N_a , and the mean value, N_m , of the normal stress component related to the critical plane, are computed in S , lying on such a plane. Note that the orientation of the critical plane is assumed to be correspondent to the crack initiation plane.

Then, by employing N_a and N_m , the amplitude of an equivalent normal stress component, $N_{eq,a}$, is computed by means of the following equation:

$$N_{eq,a} = N_a + \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_m}{\sigma_u} \right) \quad (1)$$

being $\sigma_{af,-1}$ the material fatigue strength at a reference number of loading cycles, N_0 , under fully reversed normal loading, and σ_u the ultimate tensile strength of the material. Moreover, the amplitude, C_a , of the shear stress component lying on the critical plane is computed in S , by employing the Maximum Rectangular Hull method [61].

The number of loading cycles to failure, N_{cal} , may be computed through the following equation, by employing an iterative procedure:

$$\sqrt{N_{eq,a}^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{N_{cal}}{N_0}\right)^{-2/m} \left(\frac{N_0}{N_{cal}}\right)^{-2/m^*}} C_a^2 = \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_{cal}}{N_0}\right)^{-1/m} \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_{af,-1}$ is the material fatigue strength at a reference number of loading cycles, N_0 , under fully reversed shear loading, and m and m^* are the slopes of the S-N curve under fully reversed normal and shear loading, respectively.

4. THEORETICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental tests listed in **Tables 2** and **3** are simulated by means of the criterion described in Section 3.2, allowing to:

- i) estimate the crack initiation direction, θ_{cal} ;
- ii) estimate the number of loading cycles to failure, N_{cal} .

4.1 Crack initiation direction

For each test simulated, the computed hot-spot, H , coincides with the trailing edge of the contact, in accordance with the experimental observations. In **Figure 11**, the time history of σ_1 is plotted for five material points located along the contact surface ($-1 \leq x \leq 1 \text{ mm}$ and $z=0$, see **Figure 8**) for both the specimen No. R1 and No. T1.

Figure 11.

The crack initiation direction, $\theta_{cal} = \alpha_{cr}$, ranges from 0° to 10° , for all the tests examined. In more detail, the value of θ_{cal} is equal to:

- 5° for test No. R3, characterised by constant normal load;
- 5° for test No. T3, characterised by cyclic normal load with $f_P = 1\text{Hz}$;
- 10° for test No. T8, characterised by cyclic normal load with $f_P = 5\text{Hz}$;
- 5° for test No. T13, characterised by cyclic normal load with $f_P = 10\text{Hz}$.

The cracks are predicted to initiate with a direction inward the contact region. This is in quite good agreement with the experimental findings, since the crack orientations were inward the contact region, even if lower values of crack initiation direction are estimated. Moreover, no significant correlation may be highlighted between estimated crack initiation direction and normal load frequency, in accordance with the experimental results.

4.2 Fretting fatigue lifetime

The values of the estimated fretting fatigue lifetime, N_{cal} , are listed in **Tables 2** and **3** for each test simulated.

For a given value of $\sigma_{B,max}$, it can be observed that the specimens subjected to a cyclic normal loading (see **Table 3**) are characterised by a lower value of N_{cal} with respect to those related to the reference group (see **Table 2**), with the exception of the specimens

under $\sigma_{B,\max} = 200\text{MPa}$ and 260MPa , where N_{cal} reaches its maximum value in correspondence of $f_p = 5\text{Hz}$. The value of N_{cal} increases by increasing f_p , with the exception of the specimens under $\sigma_{B,\max} = 200\text{MPa}$ and 260MPa , where N_{cal} reaches its maximum value for $f_p = 5\text{Hz}$.

Moreover, by taking as the reference lifetime that related to a constant normal load, the absolute value of the relative difference in terms of N_{cal} , computed with respect to the above reference value, is the most severe for $\sigma_{B,\max} = 130\text{MPa}$ and the less severe for $\sigma_{B,\max} = 260\text{MPa}$, although a non-monotonic trend is noted by increasing f_p , as it is shown in **Figure 12**.

Figure 12.

Such different trends with respect to those experimentally observed (see Section 2.3) may be due to the fact that in the numerical model (see Section 3.1) the friction coefficient has the same value for each value of f_p examined. A more realistic numerical model should implement a relationship of such a coefficient as a function of f_p , in order to take into account the different contact surface damage experimentally observed by increasing f_p [25]. Another possible reason for such different trends could be attributed to the fact that, the effect of compliance of the contact system has not been considered in the numerical simulation. As a matter of

fact, the compliance of the contact system is a dominant factor controlling the fretting response and plays a key role in the correct estimation of the main variables at the contact interface [62].

The comparison between the experimental number of loading cycles to failure and the estimated one is shown in **Figures 13(a)-(d)**, for each test subjected to a constant normal load (tests No. R1-R5 in **Table 2**), and a cyclic normal load with frequency equal to 1Hz , 5Hz , and 10Hz (tests No. T1-T15 in **Table 3**), respectively. Note that, the dashed lines define the scatter band 2, whereas the dot-dashed lines define the scatter band 3.

Figure 13.

The estimated fatigue life can be considered in quite good agreement with the experimental results since 95% of the estimations fall within the scatter band 2 and all the results fall within the scatter band 3.

As far as the ratio N_{cal}/N_{exp} (listed in **Tables 2** and **3**) is taken into account, it may be highlighted that conservative estimations (i.e. $N_{cal}/N_{exp} < 1$) are provided for almost half of the simulated cases. In particular, it can be noticed that the results tend to become less conservative as the experimental fatigue life increases, that is by decreasing $\sigma_{B,max}$.

Furthermore, the accuracy of the criterion can be quantified by employing the root mean square error method [63,64]. In particular, the value of the root mean square error, T_{RMS} , is calculated as:

$$T_{RMS} = 10^{E_{RMS}} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$E_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{20} \log^2 (N_{cal}/N_{exp})_i}{20}} \quad (4)$$

In the present work, the T_{RMS} value is equal to 1.54, remarking the quite good accuracy of the criterion employed in terms of fretting fatigue lifetime estimations. As a matter of fact, a T_{RMS} value equal to 1 corresponds to a perfect correlation between estimated values and experimental results.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, both crack initiation direction and fatigue lifetime of fretting fatigue experimental tests, carried out on an Al7075-T6 aluminium alloy, have been estimated. In particular, such tests are carried out in partial slip regime, by employing flat-to-flat bridge-shaped fretting pads, which are pushed against the specimen by means of either a constant or a cyclic normal load.

Different frequencies of such a cyclic load have been considered, as well as different levels of the cyclic axial load applied to the specimen.

The experimental campaign has been simulated by employing a multiaxial fatigue criterion proposed for fretting fatigue, where the stress state within the specimen, which represents one of the input data for such a criterion, is computed by means of a bi-dimensional FE numerical model.

The crack initiation location is estimated in correspondence to the trailing edge of the contact for each test analysed, in accordance with the experimental observations.

Relatively to the estimated crack initiation direction, the results are in quite good agreement with the experimental observations, since experimental cracks were observed to grow inward the contact region, although the experimental cracks were characterised by higher values of crack initiation orientation as compared to the estimated ones. Moreover, no significant correlation has been highlighted between estimated crack initiation direction and the normal load frequency, in accordance with the experimental results.

Relatively to fatigue lifetime estimation, satisfactory theoretical results have been obtained, since almost all the results fell into scatter band 2, with about half of conservative estimations.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the multiaxial criterion employed provides results characterised by a satisfactory accuracy in terms of both crack initiation direction and lifetime.

In order to obtain more accurate results, a relationship of the friction coefficient as a function of the frequency of the normal load, f_p , could be implemented in the future in the numerical model, in order to take into account the different contact surface damage experimentally observed by increasing f_p . Moreover, the implementation of parameters, such as compliance of the contact system as well as the material removal due to wear (which have been neglected in the numerical model), would improve the estimated results accuracy.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR), Research Grant PRIN 2017 No. 2017HFPKZY on 'Modelling of constitutive laws for traditional and innovative building materials'.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fuchs H. O., Stephens R. I. Metal fatigue in engineering. New York, USA: Wiley; 1980.
- [2] Carpinteri A., Brighenti R., Vantadori S., Influence of the cold-drawing process on fatigue crack growth of a V-notched round bar. *Int J Fatigue*, 2010; 32, 7: 1136-1145. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2009.12.014
- [3] Wang W., Liu H., Zhu C., Wei P., Wu W., Micromechanical analysis of gear fatigue-ratcheting damage considering the phase state and inclusion. *Tribol Int*, 2019; 136, 182-195. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2019.03.040
- [4] Wang S., Abdel Wahab M. Fretting Wear Effect on Fretting Fatigue by Findley Parameter in Mixed Slip Regime. *Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*, 2021: 647-656. DOI: 10.1007/978-981-15-9893-7_48.
- [5] Hills D.A., Nowell D. Mechanics of fretting fatigue. Dordrecht, Netherlands: Kluwer academic publisher; 1994.
- [6] Waterhouse R., Lindley T. Fretting fatigue. London, UK: ESIS Publications; 1994.
- [7] Carpinteri A., Vantadori S., Zanichelli A., Lifetime estimation of mechanical assemblies under constant amplitude fretting fatigue loading. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct*, 2019; 42: 1927-1936. DOI: 10.1111/ffe.13043
- [8] Araújo J.A., Castro F.C., Pommier S., Bellecave J., Mériaux J., Equivalent configurations for notch and fretting fatigue. *Frattura ed Integrità Strutturale*, 2015; 9, 33: 427-433. DOI: 10.3221/IGF-ESIS.33.47
- [9] Szolwinski M.P., Farris T.N., Mechanics of fretting fatigue crack formation. *Wear*, 1996; 198: 93-107. DOI: 10.1016/0043-1648(96)06937-2.
- [10] Araújo J.A., Castro F.C., Pommier S., Bellecave J., Mériaux J., On the design and test of equivalent configurations for notch and fretting fatigue. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct*, 2016; 39, 10: 1241-1250. DOI: 10.1111/ffe.12435
- [11] Collins J.A., Fretting-fatigue damage-factor determination. *J Eng Ind*, 1965; 87, 3: 298-302. DOI: 10.1115/1.3670822
- [12] Ruiz C., Boddington P.H.B., Chen K.C., An investigation of fatigue and fretting in a dovetail joint. *Exp Mech*, 1984; 24: 208-17. DOI: 10.1007/BF02323167
- [13] Rajasekaran R., Nowell D., Fretting fatigue in dovetail blade roots: experiment and analysis. *Tribol Int*, 2006; 39: 1277-85. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2006.02.044
- [14] Santus C., Fretting fatigue of aluminum alloy in contact with steel in oil drill pipe connections, modeling to interpret test results. *Int J Fatigue*, 2008; 30, 4: 677-688. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2007.05.006
- [15] Azevedo C.R.F., Henriques A.M.D., Pulino Filho A.R., Ferreira J.L.A., Araújo J.A., Fretting fatigue in overhead conductors: Rig design and failure analysis of a Grosbeak aluminium cable steel reinforced conductor. *Eng Fail Anal*, 2009; 16, 1: 136-151, DOI: 10.1016/j.engfailanal.2008.01.003

- [16] O'Halloran S.M., Connaire A.D., Harte A.M., Leen S.B., A global-local fretting analysis methodology and design study for the pressure armour layer of dynamic flexible marine risers. *Tribol Int*, 2020; 142, 105967. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2019.105967
- [17] Nowell D., Dini D., Hills D.A., Recent developments in the understanding of fretting fatigue. *Eng Fract Mech*, 2006; 73: 207-222. DOI: 10.1016/j.engfracmech.2005.01.013
- [18] Nesládek M., Španiel M., Jurenka J., Růžička J., Kuželka J., Fretting fatigue experimental and numerical approaches. *Int J Fatigue*, 2012; 44: 61-73. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2012.05.015
- [19] Warmuth A.R., Pearson S.R., Shipway P.H., Sun W., The effect of contact geometry on fretting wear rates and mechanisms for a high strength steel. *Wear*, 2013; 301: 491-500. DOI: 10.1016/j.wear.2013.01.018
- [20] Martín V., Vázquez J., Navarro C., Domínguez J., Fretting fatigue analysis of shot-peened Al 7075-T651 test specimens. *Metals*, 2019; 9: 586. DOI: 10.3390/met9050586
- [21] Chen X., Zhai W., Dong S., Zheng K., Xu R., Wang J., Liu X., Lu W., Investigations on torsional fretting wear properties of CuAlNi processed by ultrasonic vibration-assisted milling. *Tribol Int*, 2020; 146, 106238. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2020.106238
- [22] Abbasi F., Majzooobi G.H., An investigation into the effect of elevated temperatures on fretting fatigue response under cyclic normal contact loading. *Theor Appl Fract Mech*, 2017; 91: 37-43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tafmec.2017.07.018
- [23] Lavella M., Partial-gross slip fretting transition of martensitic stainless steels. *Tribol Int*, 2020; 146, 106163. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2020.106163
- [24] Rossino L.S., Castro F.C., Bose Filho W.W., Araújo J.A., Issues on the mean stress effect in fretting fatigue of a 7050-T7451 Al alloy posed by new experimental data. *Int J Fatigue*, 2009; 31, 11-12: 2041-2048. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2008.12.011
- [25] Majzooobi G.H., Abbasi F., An Investigation into the effect of normal load frequency on fretting fatigue behavior of Al7075-T6. *Tribol Trans*, 2017. DOI: 10.1080/10402004.2017.1371366
- [26] Nishioka K., Hirakawa K., Fundamental Investigations of Fretting Fatigue: Part 6, Effects of Contact Pressure and Hardness of Materials. *Bull JSME*, 1972; 15: 135-44. DOI: 10.1299/jsme1958.15.135
- [27] Bramhall R. Studies in fretting fatigue. D.Phil. thesis, University of Oxford; 1973.
- [28] Nowell D. An analysis of fretting fatigue. D.Phil. thesis, University of Oxford; 1988.
- [29] Wittkowsky B.U., Birch P.R., Domínguez J., Suresh S., Experimental investigation of fretting fatigue with spherical contact in 7075-T6 aluminum alloy. *ASTM Special Technical Publication*, 2000; 1367: 213-227. DOI: 10.1520/stp14731s
- [30] Vázquez J., Navarro C., Domínguez J. Experimental results in fretting fatigue with shot and laser peened Al 7075-T651 specimens. *Int J Fatigue*, 2012; 40: 143-53. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2011.12.014

- [31] Majzoobi G.H., Hojjati R., Nematian M., Zalnejad E., Ahmadkhani A.R., Hanifepoor E., A new device for fretting fatigue testing. *Transactions of The Indian Institute of Metals*, 2010; 63, 2-3: 493-497.
- [32] Noraphaiphaksa N., Manonukul A., Kanchanomai C., Fretting Fatigue with Cylindrical-On-Flat Contact: Crack Nucleation, Crack Path and Fatigue Life. *Metals*, 2017; 10, 155. DOI: 10.3390/ma10020155
- [33] Almeida G.M.J., Pessoa G.C.V., Cardoso R.A., Castro F.C., Araújo J.A., Investigation of crack initiation path in AA7050-T7451 under fretting conditions. *Tribol Int*, 2020; 144, 106103. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2019.106103
- [34] Pinto A.L., Cardoso R.A., Talemi R., Araújo J.A., Fretting fatigue under variable amplitude loading considering partial and gross slip regimes: Numerical analysis. *Tribol Int*, 2020; 146, 106199. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2020.106199
- [35] Attis M.H., Waterhouse R.B., Standardization of fretting fatigue test methods and equipment. ASTM International, 1992.
- [36] Hutson A.L., Chambon L., Observations of fretting fatigue micro-damage of Ti-6Al-4V. *Wear*, 2003; 255: 259-268. DOI: 10.1016/S0043-1648(03)00152-2
- [37] Golden P.J., Shepard M.J., Life prediction of fretting fatigue with advanced surface treatments. *Mat Sci Eng A*, 2007; 468-470: 15-22. DOI: 10.1016/j.msea.2006.10.168
- [38] Prevey P.S., Jayaraman N., Ravindranath R.A., Shepard M., Mitigation of fretting fatigue damage in blade and disk pressure faces with low plasticity burnishing. *J Eng Gas Turb Power*, 2010; 132: 082105. DOI: 10.1115/1.2943154
- [39] Navarro C., Muñoz S., Domínguez J., Fracture mechanics approach to fretting fatigue behaviour of coated aluminium alloy components. *J Strain Anal Eng*, 2014; 49: 66-75. DOI: 10.1177/0309324713509092
- [40] Infante-García D., Llavori I., Zabala A., Giner E. The minimum shear stress range criterion and its application to crack orientation prediction in incomplete contact fretting problems. *Int J Fatigue*, 2019; 129, art. no. 105223. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2019.105223
- [41] Vázquez J., Carpinteri A., Bohórquez L., Vantadori S., Fretting fatigue investigation on Al 7075-T651 alloy: Experimental, analytical and numerical analysis. *Tribol Int*, 2019; 135: 478-487. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2019.03.028
- [42] Vantadori S., Almeida G.M.J., Fortese G., Pessoa G.C.V., Araújo J.A., Early fretting crack orientation by using the critical plane approach. *Int J Fatigue*, 2018; 114: 282-288. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2018.04.015
- [43] Erena D., Vázquez J., Navarro C., Domínguez J., Numerical analysis of toroidal voids as stress relievers in shrink-fitted shafts. *Tribol Int*, 2020; 143, 105996. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2019.105996
- [44] Zanichelli A., Vantadori S., Shot-peened fretting fatigue components: endurance strength and fatigue life assessment. *Material Design and Processing Communications*, 2020; 196: 1-5. DOI: 10.1002/mdp2.196

- [45] Vantadori S., Vázquez J., Zanichelli A., Carpinteri A., Luciano R., Structural integrity of shot peened Ti6Al4V specimens. *Int J Fracture*, 2021; In press. DOI: 10.1007/s10704-021-00523-0.
- [46] Iyer K., Mall S., Effects of cyclic frequency and contact pressure on fretting fatigue under two-level block loading. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct*, 2000; 23: 335-346. DOI: 10.1046/j.1460-2695.2000.00288.x
- [47] Lee H., Mall S., Investigation into effects and interaction of various fretting fatigue variables under slip-controlled mode. *Trib Int*, 2006; 39: 1213-1219. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2006.02.011
- [48] Talemi R., Wahab M.A., De Pauw J., De Baets P., Prediction of fretting fatigue crack initiation and propagation lifetime for cylindrical contact configuration. *Trib Int*, 2014; 76: 73-91. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2014.02.017
- [49] Bhatti N.A., Wahab M.A., Finite element analysis of fretting fatigue under out of phase loading conditions. *Trib Int*, 2017; 109: 552-562. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2017.01.022
- [50] Bhatti N.A., Pereira K., Wahab M.A., A continuum mechanics approach for fretting fatigue under out of phase loading. *Trib Int*, 2018; 117: 39-51. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2017.08.009
- [51] Abbasi F., Majzoobi G.H., Effect of out-of-phase loading on fretting fatigue response of Al7075-T6 under cyclic normal loading using a new testing apparatus. *Eng Fract Mech*, 2018; 188: 93-111. DOI: 10.1016/j.engfracmech.2017.08.010
- [52] Vantadori S., Vázquez J., Zanichelli A., Fretting fatigue and shot peening: a multiaxial fatigue criterion including residual stress relaxation. *Tribol Int*, 2020; 151: 106537. DOI: 10.1016/j.triboint.2020.106537
- [53] Vantadori S., Zanichelli A., Araújo J.A., Fretting fatigue of 7050-t7451 al alloy: the influence of bulk mean stress. *Int J Fatigue*, 2020; 140: 105816. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2020.105816
- [54] Vantadori S., Zanichelli A., Fretting-fatigue analysis of shot-peened aluminium and titanium test specimens. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct*, 2021; 44, 2: 397-409. DOI: 10.1111/ffe.13367
- [55] Souaï N., Bozzolo N., Nazé L., Chastel Y., Logé R., About the possibility of grain boundary engineering via hot-working in a nickel-base superalloy. *Scr Mater*, 2010; 62: 851-854. DOI: 10.1016/j.scriptamat.2010.02.019
- [56] Naderi M., Hoseini S.H., Khonsari M.M., Probabilistic simulation of fatigue damage and life scatter of metallic components. *Int J Plasticity*, 2013; 43: 101-115. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijplas.2012.11.001
- [57] Zhang J., Cheng X., Xia Q., Yan C., Strengthening effect of laser shock peening on 7075-T6 aviation aluminum alloy. *Adv Mech Eng*, 2020; 12, 8. DOI: 10.1177/1687814020952177
- [58] Souaï N., Bozzolo N., Nazé L., Chastel Y., Logé R., About the possibility of grain boundary engineering via hot-working in a nickel-base superalloy. *Scripta Materialia*, 2010; 62, 851-854. DOI: 10.1016/j.scriptamat.2010.02.019
- [59] Majzoobi G.H., Jaleh M., Duplex surface treatments on AL7075-T6 alloy against fretting fatigue behavior by application of titanium

coating plus nitriding. *Mater Sci Eng A*, 2007; 452-453: 673-81. DOI: 10.1016/j.msea.2006.11.007

[60] Araújo J.A., Almeida G.M.J., Ferreira J.L.A., da Silva C.R.M., Castro F.C., Early cracking orientation under high stress gradient: the fretting. *Int J Fatigue*, 2017; 100: 302-311. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2016.12.013

[61] Araújo J.A., Carpinteri A., Ronchei C., Spagnoli A., Vantadori S., An alternative definition of the shear stress amplitude based on the maximum rectangular hull method and application to the C-S (Carpinteri-Spagnoli) criterion. *Fatig Fract Eng Mater Struct*, 2014; 37: 764-71. DOI: 10.1111/ffe.12180

[62] Infante-García D., Marco M., Zabala A., Abbasi F., Giner E., Llavori I., On the Role of Contact and System Stiffness in the Measurement of Principal Variables in Fretting Wear Testing. *Sensors*, 2020; 20, 15: 4152. DOI: 10.3390/s20154152

[63] Vantadori S., Carpinteri A., Fortese G., Ronchei C., Scorza D., Zanichelli A., Fatigue lifetime evaluation of notched components: Implementation of the control volume concept in a strain-based LCF criterion. *Theor Appl Fract Mech*, 2018; 97, 400-408. DOI: 10.1016/j.tafmec.2017.07.001

[64] Vantadori S., Carpinteri A., Luciano R., Ronchei C., Scorza D., Zanichelli A., Mean stress effect on fatigue life estimation for Inconel 718 alloy. *Int J Fatigue*, 2020; 133, 105391. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2019.105391

NOMENCLATURE

d	average grain size
E	Young modulus
m	slope of the S-N curve under fully reversed normal loading
m^*	slope of the S-N curve under fully reversed shear loading
N_a	amplitude of the normal stress component acting on the critical plane
N_{cal}	estimated number of loading cycles to failure
N_{exp}	experimental number of loading cycles to failure
N_m	mean value of the normal stress component acting on the critical plane
$N_{eq,a}$	amplitude of the equivalent normal stress component acting on the critical plane
\bar{N}_a	averaged value of N_a
\bar{N}_m	averaged value of N_m
$\bar{N}_{eq,a}$	average value of $N_{eq,a}$
P	normal load applied to the pads
B	cyclic axial load applied to the specimen
t	time
T	period
α	orientation of a critical plane candidate
α_{cr}	orientation of the critical plane
μ	friction coefficient
ν	Poisson ratio
θ_{cal}	estimated crack orientation
θ_{exp}	experimental crack orientation

$\sigma_{af,-1}$	material fatigue strength under fully reversed normal loading at a reference number N_0 of loading cycles
$\sigma_{B,max}$	maximum value of the cyclic axial bulk stress
σ_u	ultimate tensile strength
$\tau_{af,-1}$	material fatigue strength under fully reversed shear loading at a reference number N_0 of loading cycles

APPENDIX A

The criterion employed in the present paper to analyse both crack initiation direction and fatigue lifetime of each test specimen is that proposed by Carpinteri et al. for fretting fatigue [52-54]. The main steps of the criterion are hereafter summarised.

Once the stress field is computed, and some material fatigue properties are set (see **Table 1**), the critical plane orientation is computed by exploiting the Critical Direction Method [59]. More precisely, let us consider the flat-on-flat geometry shown in **Figure A.1**, representing the middle plane of the tested specimen.

Figure A.1.

Firstly, the hot-spot H is looked for on the contact surface (that is, $-c \leq x \leq c$). The point H is that experiencing the maximum value of the maximum principal stress, σ_1 , during the period.

Then, the reference frame $Hr\alpha$, shown in **Figure A.1**, and a segment from the point H with an orientation α are considered. The length segment is $2d$, where d is the average grain size of the material. Note that such a segment is the two-dimensional representation of a critical plane candidate.

Now, by applying the Critical Direction method **[59]**, the value of a fatigue parameter is computed, where such a parameter is represented by an average stress/strain quantity calculated along the above segment. Here, the averaged value of an equivalent normal stress amplitude, $\bar{N}_{eq,a}$, is taken as the fatigue parameter, that is:

$$\bar{N}_{eq,a}(\alpha) = \bar{N}_a(\alpha) + \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{\bar{N}_m(\alpha)}{\sigma_u} \right) \quad (\mathbf{A1})$$

where \bar{N}_a is given by:

$$\bar{N}_a(\alpha) = \frac{1}{2d} \int_0^{2d} N_a(r, \alpha) dr \quad (\mathbf{A2})$$

whereas \bar{N}_m is given by:

$$\bar{N}_m(\alpha) = \frac{1}{2d} \int_0^{2d} N_m(r, \alpha) dr \quad (\mathbf{A3})$$

where N_a and N_m are the amplitude and the mean value of the normal stress with respect to the critical plane candidate. Moreover, $\sigma_{af,-1}$ is the material fatigue strength at a reference number of loading cycles N_0 (generally assumed equal to $2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles) and σ_u the ultimate tensile strength of the material.

Note that, Eq. (A1) is based on the well-known linear interaction between the normal stress amplitude and the normal stress mean value, described by the diagram of Goodman. As a matter of fact, when a tensile mean stress is superimposed to an alternating stress, a detrimental effect is generally observed. On the other hand, it has been observed that a compressive mean stress may have a beneficial effect on the fatigue strength of several steels and aluminium. Consequently, the Goodman relationship may be extrapolated also for negative values of the mean stress [52]. It is important to highlight that such an extrapolation is allowed, provided that the stress level remains beneath the material yielding stress.

Finally, the critical plane orientation is taken as that orientation maximising the fatigue parameter, as dictated by the Critical Direction method. Therefore, the critical plane is here taken as that plane with an orientation, α_{cr} , that maximizes $\bar{N}_{eq,a}$, that is:

$$\bar{N}_{eq,a}(\alpha_{cr}) = \max_{-90^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ} \{ \bar{N}_{eq,a}(\alpha) \} \quad (\mathbf{A4})$$

Note that, in order to perform such a maximisation, a suitable angular increment has to be fixed so that, by starting with a value of $\alpha=0^\circ$ and up to values of $\pm 90^\circ$, the whole specimen region is investigated.

Once the critical plane is determined, fretting fatigue assessment is performed on such a plane. More precisely, the material point S (**Figure A.1**) where to perform such an assessment is far $2d$ from the hot-spot H . At such a point, both the amplitude, $N_a(2d, \alpha_{cr})$, and the mean value, $N_m(2d, \alpha_{cr})$, of the normal stress are computed, together with the amplitude of the shear stress, $C_a(2d, \alpha_{cr})$.

Note that N_a and N_m can be readily computed since the direction of the normal stress is fixed with respect to time, whereas the definition of C_a can be different, due to the fact that the shear stress describes a closed path on the critical plane during a loading cycle. Therefore, the computation of C_a according to the Maximum Rectangular Hull method [60] is implemented in the criterion.

The lifetime is worked out by solving the following equation with an iterative procedure:

$$\sqrt{\left\{ N_a(2d, \alpha_{cr}) + \sigma_{af,-1} \left[\frac{N_m(2d, \alpha_{cr})}{\sigma_u} \right] \right\}^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{N_{cal}}{N_0} \right)^{-2/m} \left(\frac{N_0}{N_{cal}} \right)^{-2/m^*} C_a^2(2d, \alpha_{cr})} = \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_{cal}}{N_0} \right)^{-1/m} \quad (\text{A5})$$

where m and m^* are the slopes of S-N curves for fully reversed normal and shear stress, respectively, and $\tau_{af,-1}$ is the material fatigue strength at a reference number of loading cycles N_0 .

Figure 1. Typical arrangements for fretting fatigue testing with:
 (a) stand-alone pads (sphere-to-flat configuration) and (b)
 bridge-shaped pads (flat-to-flat configuration).
 In each configuration the specimen is subjected to cyclic tension.

Figure 2. (a) Fretting apparatus employed for fretting fatigue tests [25] and (b) detail of the holder disks.

Figure 3. (a) Test specimen and (b) bridge-shaped pad (sizes in mm).

Figure 4. Time history of both the cyclic normal load and the cyclic bulk axial load, normalised with respect to P_{max} and B_{max} , respectively, for different values of f_P (that is, 1, 5, and 10Hz).

Table 1. Mechanical and fatigue properties of Al 7075-T6 alloy [25,56] and SS 410 stainless steel [25].

MATERIAL	E [GPa]	ν	σ_y [MPa]	σ_u [MPa]	$\sigma_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	m	$\tau_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	m^*	N_0 [cycles]
Al 7050-T6	71	0.33	520	580	178	7.12	103	7.12	$2 \cdot 10^6$
SS 410	210	0.3	420	700	-	-	-	-	-

Table 2. Loading parameters, experimental and estimated fretting fatigue life for the specimens No. R1-R5 (named reference group), subjected to a constant normal load, $P=1200N$. The ratio between

N_{cal} / N_{exp} is also reported.

TEST No.	P [N]	$\sigma_{B,m}$ [MPa]	$\sigma_{B,a}$ [MPa]	N_{exp} [cycles]	N_{cal} [cycles]	$\frac{N_{cal}}{N_{exp}}$
R1	1200	65	65	2.05E+05	4.01E+05	1.95
R2	1200	75	75	1.83E+05	2.26E+05	1.24
R3	1200	90	90	1.33E+05	1.13E+05	0.85
R4	1200	100	100	1.19E+05	8.11E+04	0.68
R5	1200	130	130	6.79E+04	3.89E+04	0.57

Table 3. Loading parameters, experimental and estimated fretting fatigue life for the specimens No. T1-T15, subjected to a cyclic normal load, P . The ratio between N_{cal}/N_{exp} is also reported.

TEST No.	P_m [N]	P_a [N]	f_P [Hz]	$\sigma_{B,m}$ [MPa]	$\sigma_{B,a}$ [MPa]	N_{exp} [cycles]	N_{cal} [cycles]	$\frac{N_{cal}}{N_{exp}}$
T1	600	600	1	65	65	9.84E+04	2.66E+05	2.70
T2	600	600	1	75	75	9.36E+04	1.55E+05	1.66
T3	600	600	1	90	90	7.58E+04	8.45E+04	1.11
T4	600	600	1	100	100	7.29E+04	6.24E+04	0.86
T5	600	600	1	130	130	4.88E+04	3.06E+04	0.63
T6	600	600	5	65	65	1.03E+05	1.55E+05	1.50
T7	600	600	5	75	75	9.76E+04	1.60E+05	1.63
T8	600	600	5	90	90	8.92E+04	1.49E+05	1.67
T9	600	600	5	100	100	8.03E+04	1.21E+05	1.51
T10	600	600	5	130	130	4.99E+04	5.00E+04	1.00
T11	600	600	10	65	65	1.22E+05	1.21E+05	0.99
T12	600	600	10	75	75	1.10E+05	1.20E+05	1.10
T13	600	600	10	90	90	8.77E+04	7.24E+04	0.83
T14	600	600	10	100	100	8.19E+04	5.54E+04	0.68
T15	600	600	10	130	130	5.29E+04	3.33E+04	0.63

Figure 5. Crack initiation site at the contact trailing edge of the specimen.

Figure 6. Experimental crack initiation direction for tests No.: (a) R3, (b) T3, (c) T8 and (d) T13.

Figure 7. Relative variation of N_{exp} versus the normal load frequency, f_p , computed with respect to the reference lifetime, by varying the maximum value of the axial cyclic stress, $\sigma_{B,max}$.

Figure 8. FE model employed to compute the specimen stress state, where u_x and u_z represent the displacement along X and Z, respectively.

Figure 9. Specimen No. R1: stress field in close proximity of the contact surface ($-1.5 \leq x \leq 1.5 \text{ mm}$ and $z=0$) at different time instants during the fretting cycle period equal to 0.1sec.

Figure 10. Specimen No. T1: stress field in close proximity of the contact surface ($-1.5 \leq x \leq 1.5 \text{ mm}$ and $z=0$) at different time instants during the fretting cycle period equal to 1 sec.

Figure 11. Time history of σ_1 in five material points located along the contact surface ($-1 \leq x \leq 1 \text{ mm}$ and $z=0$, see Figure 8) for the specimen (a) No. R1 and (b) No. T1. The curves in red are related to the estimated hot-spot point, H .

Figure 12. Relative variation of N_{cat} versus the normal load frequency, f_p , computed with respect to the reference lifetime, by varying the maximum value of the axial cyclic stress, $\sigma_{B,max}$.

Figure 13. Experimental vs estimated fatigue life for the specimens subjected to: (a) a constant normal load, and a cyclic normal load with a frequency alternatively equal to (b) 1 Hz, (c) 5 Hz, (d) 10 Hz.

Figure A.1. Multiaxial criterion for fretting fatigue [52–54]:
determination of the critical plane.